

Verifying W states via 2-local symmetry tests with constant copy complexity

Hyunho Cha and Jungwoo Lee

NextQuantum and Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering
Seoul National University, Seoul 08826, Republic of Korea
{ovalavo, junglee}@snu.ac.kr

Abstract

Quantum state verification is a statistically reliable way to test whether an experimental device prepares a desired quantum state, without reconstructing the full density matrix. We study nonadaptive, single-copy verification of the n -qubit W state. An existing local verifier for this setting has spectral gap $O(1/n)$, so its copy complexity grows linearly with n . Motivated by the recent Bell-matching verification for GHZ states, we introduce an analogous verifier based on disjoint two-qubit measurements. Its spectral gap is $1/2$ for odd n and approximately $1/2$ for even n . Thus increasing the allowed measurement locality by just one makes the spectral gap bounded away from zero. Consequently, the copy complexity becomes independent of n . The same measurement also yields a fidelity estimation algorithm. By retaining an additional indicator from the outcome, we obtain an unbiased estimator of the W-state fidelity with copy complexity independent of the number of qubits.

1 Introduction

A quantum source is often designed to emit a particular state. Noise, calibration drift, crosstalk, and imperfect gates can make the actually produced state differ from the intended one. Full quantum state tomography tries to reconstruct the whole density matrix, but the number of real parameters of an n -qubit density matrix grows as $4^n - 1$. When the goal is only to check closeness to one known target state, tomography is usually far more expensive than necessary. *Quantum state verification* replaces tomography by repeated pass/fail tests targeted to one state [1–4].

This work is inspired by the 2-local GHZ verification in [5]. Its Bell-Matching Certification protocol verifies the n -qubit GHZ state using disjoint Bell measurements, plus one single-qubit X measurement when n is odd. The important conceptual observation is that a very small strengthening of the measurement model, namely from single-qubit measurements to two-qubit measurements, already enables a near-optimal verification spectral gap.

We ask the analogous question for the W state. The W state is the one-excitation Dicke state. Dicke states were introduced in the study of collective radiation [6], and the three-qubit W state appears as one of the two inequivalent types of genuine tripartite entanglement [7]. Efficient verification of W and Dicke states was developed by Liu et al. [8]. Later work on phased Dicke states by Li et al. [9], together with the universal approach based on Schmidt decomposition and mutually unbiased bases due to Li and Zhu [10], provides further efficient protocols.

Against this background, we show that the same modest increase in measurement locality that is effective for GHZ verification also has a strong analog for W states. We construct a verifier that randomly groups the qubits into disjoint pairs, with one leftover qubit when necessary, and checks only the coarse symmetry pattern expected from a single excitation shared across all qubits. The protocol has a spectral gap bounded away from zero for every system size, so the number of copies required for certification depends on the desired accuracy and confidence

but *not* on the number of qubits. This demonstrates that verification of W states can be made dramatically more efficient by allowing simple disjoint two-qubit tests.

Beyond certification, our construction also gives a fidelity estimation procedure with constant copy complexity. The estimator uses the same disjoint two-qubit measurements as the verifier, but keeps one additional single-excitation indicator from the outcome. Combining this indicator with the verification pass indicator gives an unbiased estimate of the fidelity with the W state.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Fidelity

An n -qubit pure state is a unit vector in

$$\mathcal{H}_n = (\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}.$$

For a bit string $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \{0, 1\}^n$, write

$$|x\rangle = |x_1\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |x_n\rangle.$$

These 2^n vectors form an orthonormal basis of \mathcal{H}_n . The Hamming weight of x , denoted $\text{wt}(x)$, is the number of positions at which $x_i = 1$.

The fidelity of a density matrix ρ with respect to a pure target $|\psi\rangle$ is

$$F_\psi(\rho) = \langle \psi | \rho | \psi \rangle.$$

The infidelity is $1 - F_\psi(\rho)$.

2.2 Measurements and pass effects

A two-outcome quantum test is represented by an operator T satisfying

$$0 \leq T \leq I.$$

The outcome called “pass” occurs with probability

$$\text{Tr}(T\rho)$$

on input state ρ . The other outcome, “fail”, is represented by $I - T$.

When T is a projector, the test is a projective pass/fail test. More generally, if we first perform a fine-grained projective measurement and then accept some set of outcomes, the resulting pass effect is the sum of the projectors corresponding to the accepted outcomes.

2.3 Verification operators and spectral gaps

A verification protocol may randomly choose one test from a list. If test T_a is chosen with probability p_a , the average pass effect is

$$\Omega = \sum_a p_a T_a.$$

This operator is called the verification operator. The target $|\psi\rangle$ has perfect completeness if

$$T_a |\psi\rangle = |\psi\rangle \quad \text{for every test used with positive probability.}$$

Equivalently, because each $T_a \leq I$, perfect completeness is equivalent to

$$\Omega |\psi\rangle = |\psi\rangle.$$

Definition 1. Assume that $0 \leq \Omega \leq I$ and $\Omega|\psi\rangle = |\psi\rangle$. The second eigenvalue of Ω relative to $|\psi\rangle$ is

$$\beta(\Omega, \psi) = \max\{\langle v|\Omega|v\rangle : \|v\| = 1, \langle \psi | v\rangle = 0\}.$$

The spectral gap is

$$\nu(\Omega, \psi) = 1 - \beta(\Omega, \psi).$$

When the target is clear, we write simply $\beta(\Omega)$ and $\nu(\Omega)$.

Lemma 1 ([2]). Let Ω be a verification operator with perfect completeness for a pure target $|\psi\rangle$, and let $\nu = \nu(\Omega, \psi)$. Consider N independent single-copy tests, each using the same verification operator Ω , and accept the source only if every test passes. Suppose the tested states are ρ_1, \dots, ρ_N , not necessarily identical, and their average infidelity is at least ε :

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{r=1}^N (1 - F_\psi(\rho_r)) \geq \varepsilon.$$

Then it is enough to take

$$N \geq \left\lceil \frac{\ln \delta}{\ln(1 - \nu\varepsilon)} \right\rceil$$

to make the failure probability at most δ .

3 The W state and a disjoint 2-local verifier

3.1 The single-excitation subspace

For $1 \leq i \leq n$, let $|\tilde{i}\rangle$ denote the computational basis vector with a single excitation at position i :

$$|\tilde{i}\rangle = |0\rangle^{\otimes(i-1)} \otimes |1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle^{\otimes(n-i)}.$$

The single-excitation subspace is

$$\mathcal{H}_1 = \text{span}\{|\tilde{1}\rangle, \dots, |\tilde{n}\rangle\}.$$

Let

$$P_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n |\tilde{i}\rangle\langle\tilde{i}|$$

be the projector onto \mathcal{H}_1 .

Definition 2. For $n \geq 2$, the n -qubit W state is

$$|W_n\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \sum_{i=1}^n |\tilde{i}\rangle.$$

3.2 Quasi-perfect matchings

Definition 3. A quasi-perfect matching M of the vertex set $\{1, \dots, n\}$ is defined as follows.

- If n is even, M is a perfect matching: a partition of all n vertices into $n/2$ unordered pairs.
- If n is odd, M is a near-perfect matching: a partition of $n - 1$ vertices into $(n - 1)/2$ unordered pairs, together with one unmatched singleton.

We sample M uniformly from all such matchings.

For a pair $\{i, j\}$, define the normalized symmetric and antisymmetric one-excitation pair states inside the full n -qubit Hilbert space by

$$|w_{ij}^+\rangle = \frac{|\tilde{i}\rangle + |\tilde{j}\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad |w_{ij}^-\rangle = \frac{|\tilde{i}\rangle - |\tilde{j}\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}.$$

For a singleton $\{s\}$, define

$$|w_s\rangle = |\tilde{s}\rangle.$$

Algorithm 1

- 1: Sample a uniformly random quasi-perfect matching M of the n qubits.
- 2: **for** every pair $\{i, j\} \in M$ **do**
- 3: Measure that pair in the orthonormal basis

$$|00\rangle, \quad |w^+\rangle = \frac{|01\rangle + |10\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad |w^-\rangle = \frac{|01\rangle - |10\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad |11\rangle.$$

- 4: **end for**
 - 5: **if** n is odd **then**
 - 6: Measure the singleton in the computational basis $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$.
 - 7: **end if**
 - 8: Accept when the block outcomes contain one W-consistent excitation block and all other blocks are zero blocks. More explicitly:
 - a pair outcome $|w^+\rangle$ counts as one W-consistent excitation block;
 - a singleton outcome $|1\rangle$ counts as one W-consistent excitation block;
 - a pair outcome $|00\rangle$ and a singleton outcome $|0\rangle$ count as zero blocks;
 - any pair outcome $|w^-\rangle$ or $|11\rangle$ is rejected;
 - more than one W-consistent excitation block is rejected.
-

3.3 The pair-matching protocol

A single round of our verification protocol is described in Algorithm 1. Let T_M be the pass effect for matching M , and define

$$\Omega_{2\text{loc}} = \mathbb{E}_M[T_M].$$

Lemma 2. *For a fixed quasi-perfect matching M , the pass effect of Algorithm 1 is the projector*

$$T_M = \sum_{B \in M} |w_B\rangle\langle w_B|,$$

where

$$|w_B\rangle = \begin{cases} |w_{ij}^+\rangle, & B = \{i, j\} \text{ is a pair,} \\ |\tilde{s}\rangle, & B = \{s\} \text{ is a singleton.} \end{cases}$$

Proof. The measurement for a fixed matching is a projective measurement whose fine-grained outcomes are tensor products of the chosen block-basis vectors. The accepted outcomes are the following:

- for each pair block $B = \{i, j\}$, the vector with outcome $|w^+\rangle$ on that pair and outcome $|00\rangle$ on every other pair, and, if present, outcome $|0\rangle$ on the singleton;
- for the singleton block $B = \{s\}$, the vector with outcome $|1\rangle$ on the singleton and outcome $|00\rangle$ on every pair.

The first vector is $(|\tilde{i}\rangle + |\tilde{j}\rangle)/\sqrt{2} = |w_{ij}^+\rangle$ in the full n -qubit Hilbert space. The second vector is $|\tilde{s}\rangle$. The pass effect is the sum of the orthogonal rank-one projectors onto the accepted outcome vectors. This proves the formula. \square

Lemma 3 (Perfect completeness for every matching). *For every quasi-perfect matching M ,*

$$T_M|W_n\rangle = |W_n\rangle.$$

Hence Algorithm 1 has perfect completeness.

Proof. For a block $B \in M$, let $|B|$ denote its size: $|B| = 2$ for a pair and $|B| = 1$ for a singleton. By the definitions,

$$\sqrt{\frac{|B|}{n}}|w_B\rangle = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}(|\tilde{i}\rangle + |\tilde{j}\rangle), & B = \{i, j\}, \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}|\tilde{s}\rangle, & B = \{s\}. \end{cases}$$

Since the blocks of M partition all vertices, summing over blocks gives

$$|W_n\rangle = \sum_{B \in M} \sqrt{\frac{|B|}{n}}|w_B\rangle. \quad (1)$$

By Lemma 2, T_M is the projector onto the span of the mutually orthonormal vectors $\{|w_B\rangle : B \in M\}$. Equation (1) shows that $|W_n\rangle$ lies in this span. Therefore $T_M|W_n\rangle = |W_n\rangle$. \square

3.4 Derivation of the spectral gap

Theorem 1. *For $n \geq 3$, Algorithm 1 has second eigenvalue*

$$\beta(\Omega_{2\text{loc}}, W_n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n-2}{2(n-1)}, & n \text{ even}, \\ \frac{1}{2}, & n \text{ odd}, \end{cases}$$

and spectral gap

$$\nu(\Omega_{2\text{loc}}, W_n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2(n-1)}, & n \text{ even}, \\ \frac{1}{2}, & n \text{ odd}. \end{cases}$$

Proof. By Lemma 3, the eigenvalue on $|W_n\rangle$ is 1. It remains to find the largest eigenvalue on the orthogonal complement.

For every matching M , Lemma 2 shows that the range of T_M is contained in the single-excitation subspace \mathcal{H}_1 . Therefore T_M annihilates \mathcal{H}_1^\perp , and so does the average $\Omega_{2\text{loc}}$. It is enough to diagonalize $\Omega_{2\text{loc}}$ on \mathcal{H}_1 .

First assume that n is even. In a uniformly random perfect matching, every unordered pair $\{i, j\}$ appears with probability $1/(n-1)$, since by symmetry, vertex i is equally likely to be paired with any of the other $n-1$ vertices. Hence, on \mathcal{H}_1 ,

$$\Omega_{2\text{loc}} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i < j} |w_{ij}^+\rangle\langle w_{ij}^+|.$$

Now

$$|w_{ij}^+\rangle\langle w_{ij}^+| = \frac{1}{2}(|\tilde{i}\rangle\langle\tilde{i}| + |\tilde{j}\rangle\langle\tilde{j}| + |\tilde{i}\rangle\langle\tilde{j}| + |\tilde{j}\rangle\langle\tilde{i}|).$$

Each diagonal projector $|\tilde{i}\rangle\langle\tilde{i}|$ appears in $n-1$ pairs, and each off-diagonal matrix $|\tilde{i}\rangle\langle\tilde{j}|$ with $i \neq j$ appears once with coefficient $1/2$. Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} S_+ &:= \sum_{i < j} |w_{ij}^+\rangle\langle w_{ij}^+| \\ &= \frac{n-1}{2} I_{\mathcal{H}_1} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \neq j} |\tilde{i}\rangle\langle\tilde{j}| \\ &= \frac{n-1}{2} I_{\mathcal{H}_1} + \frac{1}{2} (n|W_n\rangle\langle W_n| - I_{\mathcal{H}_1}) \\ &= \frac{n-2}{2} I_{\mathcal{H}_1} + \frac{n}{2} |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|. \end{aligned}$$

Consequently,

$$\Omega_{2\text{loc}}|_{\mathcal{H}_1} = \frac{n-2}{2(n-1)}I_{\mathcal{H}_1} + \frac{n}{2(n-1)}|W_n\rangle\langle W_n|.$$

This gives eigenvalue 1 on $|W_n\rangle$ and eigenvalue $(n-2)/2(n-1)$ on every vector in \mathcal{H}_1 orthogonal to $|W_n\rangle$. Since the operator is zero on \mathcal{H}_1^\perp , the second eigenvalue is $(n-2)/2(n-1)$.

Now assume that n is odd. A uniformly random near-perfect matching has one singleton, so each vertex is the singleton with probability $1/n$. It has $(n-1)/2$ pair blocks. Since all unordered pairs are equally likely by symmetry, the probability that a fixed pair appears is

$$\frac{(n-1)/2}{\binom{n}{2}} = \frac{1}{n}.$$

Therefore, on \mathcal{H}_1 ,

$$\Omega_{2\text{loc}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i<j} |w_{ij}^+\rangle\langle w_{ij}^+| + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{s=1}^n |\tilde{s}\rangle\langle \tilde{s}|.$$

Using the formula for S_+ computed above and $\sum_s |\tilde{s}\rangle\langle \tilde{s}| = I_{\mathcal{H}_1}$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{2\text{loc}}|_{\mathcal{H}_1} &= \frac{1}{n} \left(\frac{n-2}{2} I_{\mathcal{H}_1} + \frac{n}{2} |W_n\rangle\langle W_n| \right) + \frac{1}{n} I_{\mathcal{H}_1} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} I_{\mathcal{H}_1} + \frac{1}{2} |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|. \end{aligned}$$

Thus the eigenvalue on $|W_n\rangle$ is 1, and every vector in \mathcal{H}_1 orthogonal to $|W_n\rangle$ has eigenvalue $1/2$. Again the operator is zero on \mathcal{H}_1^\perp , so the second eigenvalue is $1/2$. \square

Corollary 1. *The leading copy complexity of Algorithm 1 is $N_{2\text{loc}} \approx 2\varepsilon^{-1} \ln \frac{1}{\delta}$.*

Proof. Substitute the spectral gaps from Theorem 1 into Lemma 1. \square

Remark 1. *Our result does not prove that Algorithm 1 is optimal among all possible 2-local verifiers. Optimizing over arbitrary two-qubit block POVMs and arbitrary classical postprocessing rules remains an interesting direction for future work.*

4 A positive lower bound on the second eigenvalue

We prove a limitation on a broad class of single-copy, nonadaptive measurement models using 2-local measurements. Every block may be measured by an arbitrary POVM, and the verifier may use an arbitrary stochastic accept/reject rule as a function of all local outcomes in that fixed measurement branch. The only locality restriction is that, in each branch, the measured blocks are disjoint and have size at most two. Unlike in the GHZ case, we will show that the spectral gap cannot be made arbitrarily close to 1 in this model.

Throughout, $n \geq 3$. Recall that

$$|W_n\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \sum_{i=1}^n |\tilde{i}\rangle, \quad P_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n |\tilde{i}\rangle\langle \tilde{i}|,$$

and that P_1 is the projector onto the single-excitation subspace \mathcal{H}_1 . We write

$$|\mathbf{0}\rangle := |0\rangle^{\otimes n}.$$

For $A \subset \{1, \dots, n\}$, let \bar{A} denote its complement. If $1 \leq |A| \leq n-1$, write $|W_A\rangle$ for the W state on the qubits indexed by A , and write $|0_A\rangle = |0\rangle^{\otimes |A|}$. Define

$$|u_A\rangle := |W_A\rangle|0_{\bar{A}}\rangle, \quad |v_A\rangle := |0_A\rangle|W_{\bar{A}}\rangle. \quad (2)$$

Then

$$|W_n\rangle = \sqrt{p_A}|u_A\rangle + \sqrt{1-p_A}|v_A\rangle, \quad p_A := \frac{|A|}{n}.$$

The normalized vector in the Schmidt support orthogonal to $|W_n\rangle$ is

$$|\eta_A\rangle := \sqrt{1-p_A}|u_A\rangle - \sqrt{p_A}|v_A\rangle.$$

We also set

$$h(\mu) := \frac{3}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{1+\mu^2}}{2\mu}, \quad \mu \in (0, 1/2].$$

In particular,

$$g_* := h\left(\frac{\sqrt{2}}{3}\right) = \frac{6 - \sqrt{22}}{4}.$$

Definition 4. A deterministic 2-local POVM test consists of a partition

$$\mathcal{B} = \{B_1, \dots, B_K\}$$

of $\{1, \dots, n\}$ into blocks satisfying $|B_j| \leq 2$, a POVM $\{M_{\omega_j}^{(j)}\}_{\omega_j}$ on each block B_j , and a classical postprocessing function

$$q(\omega_1, \dots, \omega_K) \in [0, 1].$$

The corresponding pass effect is

$$T = \sum_{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_K} q(\omega_1, \dots, \omega_K) \bigotimes_{j=1}^K M_{\omega_j}^{(j)}. \quad (3)$$

A randomized protocol is a convex combination $\Omega = \sum_a p_a T_a$ of such deterministic tests.

Lemma 4. Let T be the pass effect of a deterministic 2-local POVM test with block partition \mathcal{B} . If A is a union of blocks of \mathcal{B} , then

$$T^{\Gamma_A} \geq 0, \quad (I - T)^{\Gamma_A} \geq 0,$$

where Γ_A denotes partial transpose on the tensor factors in A .

Proof. Every product effect

$$\bigotimes_{j=1}^K M_{\omega_j}^{(j)}$$

in Eq. (3) is positive. Since A is a union of whole blocks, partial transposition on A transposes some complete local factors and leaves the remaining local factors unchanged. The transpose of a positive matrix is positive, so the partial transpose of each product effect is positive. Since the coefficients $q(\omega_1, \dots, \omega_K)$ are nonnegative, $T^{\Gamma_A} \geq 0$.

The fail effect has the analogous decomposition

$$I - T = \sum_{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_K} (1 - q(\omega_1, \dots, \omega_K)) \bigotimes_{j=1}^K M_{\omega_j}^{(j)},$$

because each local POVM sums to the identity on its block. The coefficients $1 - q(\omega_1, \dots, \omega_K)$ are also nonnegative. The same argument gives $(I - T)^{\Gamma_A} \geq 0$. \square

Lemma 5 ([5], Lemma 9). Let $\Omega = \sum_a p_a T_a$, where $p_a > 0$, $\sum_a p_a = 1$, and $0 \leq T_a \leq I$. If

$$\Omega|W_n\rangle = |W_n\rangle,$$

then

$$T_a|W_n\rangle = |W_n\rangle$$

for every branch a .

Lemma 6. Let $A \subset \{1, \dots, n\}$ satisfy $1 \leq |A| \leq n - 1$. Let T be an operator satisfying

$$0 \leq T \leq I, \quad T|W_n\rangle = |W_n\rangle, \quad T^{\Gamma_A} \geq 0, \quad (I - T)^{\Gamma_A} \geq 0.$$

Set

$$x_A := \langle \eta_A | T | \eta_A \rangle, \quad y := \langle \mathbf{0} | T | \mathbf{0} \rangle, \quad \mu_A := \sqrt{p_A(1 - p_A)}.$$

Then

$$\mu_A^2(1 - x_A)^2 \leq y(1 - y). \quad (4)$$

If $p_A \in [1/3, 2/3]$, then

$$x_A + y \geq h(\mu_A) \geq g_*.$$

Proof. Let $|u_A\rangle$ and $|v_A\rangle$ be as in Eq. (2). The vectors $|W_n\rangle$ and $|\eta_A\rangle$ form an orthonormal basis of $\text{span}\{|u_A\rangle, |v_A\rangle\}$. Since $T|W_n\rangle = |W_n\rangle$ and T is Hermitian, the compression of T to this two-dimensional subspace is diagonal in the basis $\{|W_n\rangle, |\eta_A\rangle\}$, with diagonal entries 1 and x_A . Transforming back to the basis $\{|u_A\rangle, |v_A\rangle\}$ gives

$$\langle u_A | T | v_A \rangle = \sqrt{p_A(1 - p_A)}(1 - x_A) = \mu_A(1 - x_A). \quad (5)$$

Now define the normalized two-excitation vector

$$|z_A\rangle := |W_A\rangle |W_{\bar{A}}\rangle.$$

Under partial transpose on A , the matrix element in Eq. (5) becomes the off-diagonal matrix element between $|\mathbf{0}\rangle$ and $|z_A\rangle$. More explicitly,

$$\langle \mathbf{0} | T^{\Gamma_A} | z_A \rangle = \mu_A(1 - x_A).$$

Let

$$d := \langle z_A | T^{\Gamma_A} | z_A \rangle.$$

The principal 2×2 submatrix of T^{Γ_A} on $\text{span}\{|\mathbf{0}\rangle, |z_A\rangle\}$ is positive, so

$$\mu_A^2(1 - x_A)^2 \leq yd. \quad (6)$$

Similarly, the corresponding principal submatrix of $(I - T)^{\Gamma_A} = I - T^{\Gamma_A}$ is positive, so

$$\mu_A^2(1 - x_A)^2 \leq (1 - y)(1 - d). \quad (7)$$

Equations (6) and (7) also imply $0 \leq d \leq 1$. For fixed y , the largest possible value of

$$\min\{yd, (1 - y)(1 - d)\}$$

over $d \in [0, 1]$ is $y(1 - y)$, attained at $d = 1 - y$. Hence Eq. (4) follows.

It remains to minimize the resulting lower bound on $x_A + y$. Since $0 \leq T \leq I$, we have $x_A \in [0, 1]$. From Eq. (4),

$$y \geq \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - 4\mu_A^2(1 - x_A)^2}}{2}.$$

Writing $t = 1 - x_A$, we obtain

$$x_A + y \geq \frac{3}{2} - t - \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{1 - 4\mu_A^2 t^2}, \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1.$$

When $p_A \in [1/3, 2/3]$, we have $\mu_A \geq \sqrt{2}/3$. In this range the minimum over $0 \leq t \leq 1$ is attained at

$$t = \frac{1}{2\mu_A\sqrt{1 + \mu_A^2}},$$

which lies in $[0, 1]$. Substitution gives

$$x_A + y \geq \frac{3}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{1 + \mu_A^2}}{2\mu_A} = h(\mu_A).$$

Finally, the function $h(\mu)$ is increasing on $(0, 1/2]$. Therefore $\mu_A \geq \sqrt{2}/3$ implies

$$h(\mu_A) \geq h\left(\frac{\sqrt{2}}{3}\right) = \frac{6 - \sqrt{22}}{4} = g_*.$$

□

Lemma 7. *Let \mathcal{Q} be any quasi-perfect partition of $\{1, \dots, n\}$. There is a probability distribution on unions A of blocks of \mathcal{Q} such that $p_A \in [1/3, 2/3]$ and*

$$R_{\mathcal{Q}} := \mathbb{E}_A[|\eta_A\rangle\langle\eta_A|] \leq \lambda_n(P_1 - |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|), \quad (8)$$

where

$$\lambda_n = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{n-2}, & n \text{ even,} \\ 1, & n = 3, \\ \frac{2n}{(n+1)(n-3)}, & n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, n \geq 5, \\ \frac{2n}{(n-1)^2}, & n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}, n \geq 7. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Moreover,

$$(n-1)\lambda_n \leq \frac{10}{3} \quad (n \geq 3). \quad (10)$$

Proof. For each block $B \in \mathcal{Q}$, define the normalized one-excitation block vector

$$|w_B\rangle := \frac{1}{\sqrt{|B|}} \sum_{i \in B} |\tilde{i}\rangle.$$

Let

$$E_{\mathcal{Q}} := \text{span}\{|w_B\rangle : B \in \mathcal{Q}\} \subset \mathcal{H}_1.$$

For every union A of blocks of \mathcal{Q} , the vector $|\eta_A\rangle$ belongs to $E_{\mathcal{Q}}$ and is orthogonal to $|W_n\rangle$. Hence $R_{\mathcal{Q}}$ is positive and supported in $E_{\mathcal{Q}} \cap |W_n\rangle^\perp$. It is therefore enough to compute $\|R_{\mathcal{Q}}\|_\infty$.

First suppose $n = 2m$ is even. Then \mathcal{Q} consists of m pair blocks. Choose

$$r := \left\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \right\rfloor$$

pair blocks uniformly at random, and let A be their union. Then $|A| = 2r$, so $p_A = r/m \in [1/3, 1/2]$ for every $m \geq 2$. In the orthonormal basis $\{|w_B\rangle : B \in \mathcal{Q}\}$, the vector $|W_n\rangle$ is the uniform vector $m^{-1/2} \sum_B |w_B\rangle$. The vector $|\eta_A\rangle$ has coefficient

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{m-r}{mr}}$$

on selected blocks and coefficient

$$\beta = -\sqrt{\frac{r}{m(m-r)}}$$

on unselected blocks.

Let $z = \sum_B c_B |w_B\rangle$ be any unit vector satisfying $\sum_B c_B = 0$. Then

$$\langle \eta_A | z \rangle = (\alpha - \beta) \sum_{B \subset A} c_B.$$

For a uniformly random r -subset S of $\{1, \dots, m\}$, the identity

$$\mathbb{E}_S \left| \sum_{j \in S} c_j \right|^2 = \frac{r(m-r)}{m(m-1)} \sum_{j=1}^m |c_j|^2 \quad (11)$$

holds whenever $\sum_j c_j = 0$. Indeed, expanding the square gives

$$\frac{r}{m} \sum_j |c_j|^2 + \frac{r(r-1)}{m(m-1)} \sum_{j \neq k} \bar{c}_j c_k,$$

and $\sum_{j \neq k} \bar{c}_j c_k = -\sum_j |c_j|^2$. Since

$$(\alpha - \beta)^2 = \frac{m}{r(m-r)},$$

we obtain

$$\langle z | R_{\mathcal{Q}} | z \rangle = \frac{1}{m-1}.$$

Thus

$$R_{\mathcal{Q}} = \frac{1}{m-1} (P_{E_{\mathcal{Q}}} - |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|),$$

and therefore

$$\|R_{\mathcal{Q}}\|_{\infty} = \frac{1}{m-1} = \frac{2}{n-2}.$$

This proves the even case of Eq. (9).

Now suppose $n = 2m + 1$ is odd. Let B_1, \dots, B_m be the pair blocks of \mathcal{Q} , and let B_0 be the singleton. We choose A with $|A| = m$ as follows. If m is even, choose $r = m/2$ pair blocks uniformly at random and do not include B_0 . If m is odd, choose $r = (m-1)/2$ pair blocks uniformly at random and include B_0 . In both cases $|A| = m$, so $p_A = m/(2m+1) \in [1/3, 1/2]$.

The distribution is invariant under permutations of the pair blocks. Consider the subspace

$$D := \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^m c_j |w_{B_j}\rangle : \sum_{j=1}^m c_j = 0 \right\}.$$

For $z = \sum_j c_j |w_{B_j}\rangle \in D$ with $\|z\| = 1$, the selected pair blocks have coefficient

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{2(m+1)}{(2m+1)m}},$$

and the unselected pair blocks have coefficient

$$\beta = -\sqrt{\frac{2m}{(2m+1)(m+1)}}.$$

Hence

$$(\alpha - \beta)^2 = \frac{2(2m+1)}{m(m+1)}.$$

Using Eq. (11), we get $\langle z | R_{\mathcal{Q}} | z \rangle = \lambda_{\text{diff}}$ for every unit vector $z \in D$, where

$$\lambda_{\text{diff}} = \frac{2(2m+1)r(m-r)}{m^2(m^2-1)}. \quad (12)$$

The restriction of $R_{\mathcal{Q}}$ to D is $\lambda_{\text{diff}} I_D$. If m is even, then $r = m/2$, so

$$\lambda_{\text{diff}} = \frac{2m+1}{2(m^2-1)}.$$

The remaining part of $E_{\mathcal{Q}} \cap |W_n\rangle^\perp$ is one-dimensional. Since $\text{Tr } R_{\mathcal{Q}} = 1$, its eigenvalue is

$$1 - (m-1)\lambda_{\text{diff}} = \frac{1}{2(m+1)}.$$

Thus the operator norm is $(2m+1)/2(m^2-1)$, which equals

$$\frac{2n}{(n+1)(n-3)}.$$

This is the case $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

If m is odd and $m \geq 3$, then $r = (m-1)/2$, so Eq. (12) gives

$$\lambda_{\text{diff}} = \frac{2m+1}{2m^2}.$$

The remaining eigenvalue is

$$1 - (m-1)\lambda_{\text{diff}} = \frac{m+1}{2m^2}.$$

Thus the operator norm is $(2m+1)/2m^2$, which equals

$$\frac{2n}{(n-1)^2}.$$

This is the case $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, $n \geq 7$. When $n = 3$, we have $m = 1$, and the construction chooses the singleton as A . Then $R_{\mathcal{Q}}$ is a single rank-one projector, so $\|R_{\mathcal{Q}}\|_\infty = 1$.

Combining the even and odd cases proves Eq. (9). Because $R_{\mathcal{Q}}$ is positive, supported in $|W_n\rangle^\perp \cap \mathcal{H}_1$, and has operator norm at most λ_n , inequality in Eq. (8) follows.

The uniform estimate in Eq. (10) follows directly from Eq. (9). \square

Theorem 2. *Let Ω be the verification operator of any randomized 2-local POVM protocol with an arbitrary stochastic accept/reject rule and perfect completeness for $|W_n\rangle$. Let*

$$\beta = \beta(\Omega, W_n), \quad \nu = \nu(\Omega, W_n) = 1 - \beta.$$

Then

$$\beta \geq \frac{g^*}{1 + (n-1)\lambda_n}, \tag{13}$$

with λ_n defined in Eq. (9). In particular, for every $n \geq 3$,

$$\beta \geq \frac{3(6 - \sqrt{22})}{52},$$

and therefore

$$\nu \leq 1 - \frac{3(6 - \sqrt{22})}{52} \approx 0.92 < 1.$$

Proof. Write the randomized protocol as $\Omega = \sum_a p_a T_a$, where each T_a is a deterministic 2-local pass effect and $p_a > 0$. By Lemma 5, every deterministic branch satisfies

$$T_a |W_n\rangle = |W_n\rangle.$$

Fix a branch a , and let \mathcal{B}_a be its block partition. Form a quasi-perfect coarsening \mathcal{Q}_a as follows: keep every two-qubit block of \mathcal{B}_a , pair up the single-qubit blocks arbitrarily, and

leave one single-qubit block unpaired if n is odd. Every block of \mathcal{Q}_a is a union of blocks of \mathcal{B}_a . Therefore every union A of blocks of \mathcal{Q}_a is also a union of blocks of \mathcal{B}_a . By Lemma 4, both T_a and $I - T_a$ are PPT across $A|\bar{A}$.

Average the cut inequality of Lemma 6 over the block cuts supplied by Lemma 7 for \mathcal{Q}_a . Since all these cuts satisfy $p_A \in [1/3, 2/3]$, we get

$$g_* \leq \langle \mathbf{0} | T_a | \mathbf{0} \rangle + \text{Tr}(T_a R_{\mathcal{Q}_a}).$$

Using Eq. (8),

$$\text{Tr}(T_a R_{\mathcal{Q}_a}) \leq \lambda_n \text{Tr}[T_a (P_1 - |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|)].$$

Hence

$$g_* \leq \langle \mathbf{0} | T_a | \mathbf{0} \rangle + \lambda_n \text{Tr}[T_a (P_1 - |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|)]. \quad (14)$$

Averaging Eq. (14) over a gives

$$g_* \leq \langle \mathbf{0} | \Omega | \mathbf{0} \rangle + \lambda_n \text{Tr}[\Omega (P_1 - |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|)]. \quad (15)$$

Now use the definition of β . The vector $|\mathbf{0}\rangle$ is orthogonal to $|W_n\rangle$, so

$$\langle \mathbf{0} | \Omega | \mathbf{0} \rangle \leq \beta.$$

Also, $P_1 - |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|$ is a rank- $(n-1)$ projector whose range is contained in $|W_n\rangle^\perp$. Therefore the compression of Ω to this range has all Rayleigh quotients at most β , and

$$\text{Tr}[\Omega (P_1 - |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|)] \leq (n-1)\beta.$$

Substituting these two estimates into Eq. (15) yields

$$g_* \leq (1 + (n-1)\lambda_n)\beta,$$

which proves Eq. (13).

Finally, Lemma 7 gives $(n-1)\lambda_n \leq 10/3$. Consequently,

$$\beta \geq \frac{g_*}{1 + 10/3} = \frac{3g_*}{13} = \frac{3(6 - \sqrt{22})}{52}.$$

□

Remark 2. *The preceding theorem applies to arbitrary block POVMs and arbitrary stochastic accept/reject rules, but the constant is not expected to be tight. Moreover, the restriction $n \geq 3$ is necessary for any nontrivial upper bound on the spectral gap strictly below 1. For $n = 2$, the state $|W_2\rangle = (|01\rangle + |10\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$ can be verified by the single two-qubit projective test $|W_2\rangle\langle W_2|$, which has spectral gap 1.*

5 Constant-copy fidelity estimation from pair matching

We now turn to the problem of estimating the fidelity with the W state. The desired number is the fidelity

$$F_{W_n}(\rho) = \langle W_n | \rho | W_n \rangle = \text{Tr}(|W_n\rangle\langle W_n| \rho).$$

We want an estimate \widehat{F} such that

$$\mathbb{P}[|\widehat{F} - F_{W_n}(\rho)| \leq \varepsilon] \geq 1 - \delta.$$

The copy complexity is the number of independent preparations of ρ required to guarantee this inequality.

The benchmark with no measurement restrictions is the two-outcome projective measurement

$$\{|W_n\rangle\langle W_n|, I - |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|\}.$$

One shot of this measurement produces a Bernoulli random variable whose expectation is the fidelity. Averaging Bernoulli samples gives copy complexity $O(\varepsilon^{-2} \log(1/\delta))$. The difficulty is that this measurement is a global measurement across all n qubits.

The question is whether the same copy-complexity scaling can be achieved under the much more explicit restriction that, in each round, the qubits are measured only in disjoint blocks of size at most two. We design an estimator with the following properties.

- Each copy is measured by a random pairing of qubits, using two-qubit projective measurements on pairs and one single-qubit measurement when n is odd.
- The estimator is unbiased for $F_{W_n}(\rho)$.
- Each single-copy score lies in an interval of length at most 2, uniformly in n .
- Consequently,

$$N = \left\lceil \frac{2}{\varepsilon^2} \log \frac{2}{\delta} \right\rceil$$

copies suffice for additive error ε and failure probability δ , independently of n .

Recall that the average pass operator $\Omega_{2\text{loc}}$ of the W pair-matching verifier has the form

$$\Omega_{2\text{loc}} = \beta_n P_1 + \nu_n |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|, \quad \nu_n \geq \frac{1}{2}.$$

The fine-grained measurement also gives a second classical indicator whose expectation is $\text{Tr}(P_1\rho)$. Therefore the score

$$Y = \frac{A - \beta_n B}{\nu_n}$$

has expectation

$$\mathbb{E}[Y] = \text{Tr} \left(\frac{\Omega_{2\text{loc}} - \beta_n P_1}{\nu_n} \rho \right) = \langle W_n | \rho | W_n \rangle.$$

Here A is the pair-matching pass indicator and B is the single-excitation indicator extracted from the same measurement outcome.

For one copy of ρ , perform the following measurement and classical postprocessing. The measurement is the same disjoint pair-matching measurement used in Algorithm 1. The additional feature is that we keep one more classical indicator from the fine-grained outcome.

The event $A = 1$ is the pass event of the pair-matching W verification protocol in Algorithm 1. The event $B = 1$ is not a pass/fail certification event. It is the extra information used here for fidelity estimation.

Lemma 8. *Fix a quasi-perfect matching M . Let Q_M be the effect of the event $B = 1$ in Algorithm 2. Then*

$$Q_M = P_1. \tag{16}$$

Moreover, the effect of the event $A = 1$ is the pass effect T_M from Lemma 2.

Proof. The identity for $A = 1$ is precisely Lemma 2. Now consider $B = 1$. For each pair $\{i, j\}$, the event $B = 1$ includes both possible one-excitation pair outcomes, with all other blocks zero. Their two full-state projectors sum to

$$|w_{ij}^+\rangle\langle w_{ij}^+| + |w_{ij}^-\rangle\langle w_{ij}^-| = |\tilde{i}\rangle\langle\tilde{i}| + |\tilde{j}\rangle\langle\tilde{j}|,$$

Algorithm 2

- 1: Sample a uniformly random quasi-perfect matching M of the n qubits.
- 2: **for** every pair $\{i, j\} \in M$ **do**
- 3: Measure that pair in the orthonormal basis

$$|00\rangle, \quad |w^+\rangle = \frac{|01\rangle + |10\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad |w^-\rangle = \frac{|01\rangle - |10\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad |11\rangle.$$

- 4: **end for**
 - 5: **if** n is odd **then**
 - 6: Measure the singleton in the computational basis $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$.
 - 7: **end if**
 - 8: Define a classical indicator B as follows:
 - set $B = 1$ if and only if the block outcomes contain one one-excitation block and all other blocks are zero blocks;
 - pair outcomes $|w^+\rangle$ and $|w^-\rangle$ and singleton outcome $|1\rangle$ count as one-excitation block outcomes;
 - pair outcome $|00\rangle$ and singleton outcome $|0\rangle$ count as zero block outcomes;
 - any pair outcome $|11\rangle$ forces $B = 0$.
 - 9: Define a classical indicator A as follows:
 - set $A = 1$ if and only if $B = 1$ and the unique one-excitation block is either a pair outcome $|w^+\rangle$ or a singleton outcome $|1\rangle$;
 - thus the case of a unique $|w^-\rangle$ outcome has $B = 1$ but $A = 0$.
-

because the cross terms cancel. For a singleton s , the one-excitation outcome contributes $|\tilde{s}\rangle\langle\tilde{s}|$. Summing over all blocks gives

$$Q_M = \sum_{i=1}^n |\tilde{i}\rangle\langle\tilde{i}| = P_1.$$

□

For use in the estimator, define

$$(\beta_n, \nu_n) = \begin{cases} (0, 1), & n = 2, \\ \left(\frac{n-2}{2(n-1)}, \frac{n}{2(n-1)} \right), & n \geq 4 \text{ even}, \\ \left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right), & n \geq 3 \text{ odd}. \end{cases}$$

In every case $\beta_n + \nu_n = 1$ and $\nu_n \geq 1/2$.

Proposition 1. *Let $\Omega_{2\text{loc}} = \mathbb{E}_M[T_M]$, where M is uniformly random and T_M is the pair-matching pass effect. Then, for every $n \geq 2$,*

$$\Omega_{2\text{loc}} = \beta_n P_1 + \nu_n |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|.$$

Proof. The case $n = 2$ has only one pair $\{1, 2\}$ and no singleton. Thus

$$\Omega_{2\text{loc}} = T_{\{1,2\}} = |w_{12}^+\rangle\langle w_{12}^+| = |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|,$$

so $(\beta_2, \nu_2) = (0, 1)$.

For $n \geq 3$, the proof of Theorem 1 gives the stronger operator identities

$$\Omega_{2\text{loc}} = \frac{n-2}{2(n-1)}P_1 + \frac{n}{2(n-1)}|W_n\rangle\langle W_n| \quad (n \geq 4 \text{ even})$$

and

$$\Omega_{2\text{loc}} = \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}|W_n\rangle\langle W_n| \quad (n \geq 3 \text{ odd}),$$

because $\Omega_{2\text{loc}}$ is zero on \mathcal{H}_1^\perp and P_1 is the identity on \mathcal{H}_1 . \square

Corollary 2. For every $n \geq 2$,

$$|W_n\rangle\langle W_n| = \frac{\Omega_{2\text{loc}} - \beta_n P_1}{\nu_n}.$$

Define

$$r_n = \frac{\beta_n}{\nu_n} = \begin{cases} 0, & n = 2, \\ \frac{n-2}{n}, & n \geq 4 \text{ even}, \\ 1, & n \geq 3 \text{ odd}. \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

For the outcome of one measurement round, define the real-valued score

$$Y = \frac{A - \beta_n B}{\nu_n}. \quad (18)$$

Equivalently,

$$Y = \begin{cases} 1, & A = 1, \\ -r_n, & A = 0 \text{ and } B = 1, \\ 0, & B = 0. \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

For N independent copies, let Y_1, \dots, Y_N be the corresponding independent scores and output

$$\hat{F}_N = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N Y_t.$$

Since a true fidelity lies in $[0, 1]$, one may optionally clip the output to $[0, 1]$ by defining

$$\hat{F}_N^{\text{clip}} = \min\{1, \max\{0, \hat{F}_N\}\}.$$

Clipping cannot increase the absolute error from the true fidelity.

Theorem 3. For every $n \geq 2$ and every n -qubit density matrix ρ , the score Y defined in Eq. (18) satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}[Y] = F_{W_n}(\rho) = \text{Tr}(|W_n\rangle\langle W_n|\rho).$$

Proof. Condition on a fixed matching M . By Lemma 8, the effect of $A = 1$ is T_M , and the effect of $B = 1$ is P_1 . Hence

$$\mathbb{E}[Y \mid M] = \frac{\text{Tr}(T_M \rho) - \beta_n \text{Tr}(P_1 \rho)}{\nu_n} = \text{Tr} \left(\frac{T_M - \beta_n P_1}{\nu_n} \rho \right).$$

Now average over the random matching M . Since $\mathbb{E}_M[T_M] = \Omega_{2\text{loc}}$,

$$\mathbb{E}[Y] = \text{Tr} \left(\frac{\Omega_{2\text{loc}} - \beta_n P_1}{\nu_n} \rho \right).$$

By Corollary 2, the operator in parentheses is $|W_n\rangle\langle W_n|$. \square

Corollary 3. If the N copies are independent and identically prepared in state ρ , then

$$\mathbb{E}[\hat{F}_N] = F_{W_n}(\rho).$$

6 Copy complexity of Algorithm 2 and high-fidelity behavior

Lemma 9 (Hoeffding's inequality for bounded independent variables). *Let X_1, \dots, X_N be independent real random variables with $X_t \in [a_t, b_t]$ almost surely. Let $\mu_t = \mathbb{E}[X_t]$. Then, for every $s > 0$,*

$$\mathbb{P}\left[\sum_{t=1}^N (X_t - \mu_t) \geq s\right] \leq \exp\left(-\frac{2s^2}{\sum_{t=1}^N (b_t - a_t)^2}\right).$$

Consequently,

$$\mathbb{P}\left[\left|\frac{1}{N}\sum_{t=1}^N X_t - \frac{1}{N}\sum_{t=1}^N \mu_t\right| \geq \varepsilon\right] \leq 2 \exp\left(-\frac{2N^2\varepsilon^2}{\sum_{t=1}^N (b_t - a_t)^2}\right).$$

Theorem 4. *Let $n \geq 2$. Suppose N independent copies of the same state ρ are measured by Algorithm 2. Let*

$$L_n = 1 + r_n.$$

Then

$$\mathbb{P}[|\widehat{F}_N - F_{W_n}(\rho)| \geq \varepsilon] \leq 2 \exp\left(-\frac{2N\varepsilon^2}{L_n^2}\right). \quad (20)$$

Consequently it suffices to take

$$N \geq \frac{L_n^2}{2\varepsilon^2} \log \frac{2}{\delta}.$$

Equivalently,

$$N \geq \begin{cases} \left\lceil \frac{1}{2\varepsilon^2} \log \frac{2}{\delta} \right\rceil, & n = 2, \\ \left\lceil \frac{2(n-1)^2}{n^2\varepsilon^2} \log \frac{2}{\delta} \right\rceil, & n \geq 4 \text{ even}, \\ \left\lceil \frac{2}{\varepsilon^2} \log \frac{2}{\delta} \right\rceil, & n \geq 3 \text{ odd}. \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

Proof. By Eq. (19), each score satisfies

$$Y_t \in [-r_n, 1].$$

Thus the range length is $L_n = 1 + r_n$. By Corollary 3, the mean of \widehat{F}_N is $F_{W_n}(\rho)$. Applying Lemma 9 with $a_t = -r_n$ and $b_t = 1$ for every t gives Eq. (20). Finally, Eq. (17) gives

$$L_n = \begin{cases} 1, & n = 2, \\ \frac{2(n-1)}{n}, & n \geq 4 \text{ even}, \\ 2, & n \geq 3 \text{ odd}, \end{cases}$$

which yields Eq. (21). □

Corollary 4. *For every $n \geq 2$, every n -qubit density matrix ρ , every $\varepsilon > 0$, and every $\delta \in (0, 1)$, the choice*

$$N = \left\lceil \frac{2}{\varepsilon^2} \log \frac{2}{\delta} \right\rceil \quad (22)$$

guarantees

$$\mathbb{P}[|\widehat{F}_N - F_{W_n}(\rho)| \leq \varepsilon] \geq 1 - \delta.$$

Theorem 5. *Suppose the t -th copy has state ρ_t , and the copies are independent but not necessarily identical. Let*

$$\bar{F}_N = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N F_{W_n}(\rho_t).$$

Then

$$\mathbb{E}[\hat{F}_N] = \bar{F}_N$$

and

$$\mathbb{P}[|\hat{F}_N - \bar{F}_N| \geq \varepsilon] \leq 2 \exp\left(-\frac{2N\varepsilon^2}{L_n^2}\right). \quad (23)$$

In particular, the uniform choice in Eq. (22) again guarantees $|\hat{F}_N - \bar{F}_N| \leq \varepsilon$ with probability at least $1 - \delta$.

Proof. The proof of Theorem 3 applies to each copy separately, so $\mathbb{E}[Y_t] = F_{W_n}(\rho_t)$. Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}[\hat{F}_N] = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \mathbb{E}[Y_t] = \bar{F}_N.$$

The range bound $Y_t \in [-r_n, 1]$ is independent of the state. Since the variables Y_1, \dots, Y_N are independent, Lemma 9 gives Eq. (23). \square

The estimator also has useful variance behavior, especially near the ideal W state.

Proposition 2. *Let*

$$F = F_{W_n}(\rho), \quad q = \text{Tr}(P_1\rho).$$

Then $F \leq q \leq 1$, and the single-copy score satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}[Y^2] = \begin{cases} F, & n = 2, \\ \frac{n-2}{n}q + \frac{2}{n}F, & n \geq 4 \text{ even}, \\ q, & n \geq 3 \text{ odd}. \end{cases}$$

Consequently, for independent and identically distributed copies,

$$\text{Var}(\hat{F}_N) \leq \frac{1}{N}.$$

Proof. Since $|W_n\rangle \in \mathcal{H}_1$, the projector inequality $|W_n\rangle\langle W_n| \leq P_1$ holds. Therefore

$$F = \text{Tr}(|W_n\rangle\langle W_n|\rho) \leq \text{Tr}(P_1\rho) = q \leq \text{Tr}\rho = 1.$$

Let $p_A = \mathbb{P}(A = 1)$ and $p_B = \mathbb{P}(B = 1)$. By Proposition 1 and Lemma 8,

$$p_A = \text{Tr}(\Omega_{2\text{loc}}\rho) = \beta_n q + \nu_n F, \quad p_B = \text{Tr}(P_1\rho) = q.$$

The score equals 1 on A , equals $-r_n$ on $B \setminus A$, and equals 0 outside B . Hence

$$\mathbb{E}[Y^2] = p_A + r_n^2(p_B - p_A).$$

If $n = 2$, then $r_n = 0$ and $p_A = F$, so $\mathbb{E}[Y^2] = F$. If $n \geq 3$ is odd, then $r_n = 1$, so $\mathbb{E}[Y^2] = p_B = q$. If $n \geq 4$ is even, then $\beta_n = \frac{n-2}{2(n-1)}$, $\nu_n = \frac{n}{2(n-1)}$, and $r_n = \frac{n-2}{n}$. Substituting these values into $p_A + r_n^2(p_B - p_A)$ gives $\mathbb{E}[Y^2] = \frac{n-2}{n}q + \frac{2}{n}F$. \square

Proposition 3 (Variance vanishes on the ideal W state). *For every $n \geq 2$,*

$$\text{Var}(Y) \leq L_n^2(1 - F_{W_n}(\rho)) \leq 4(1 - F_{W_n}(\rho)).$$

In particular, if $\rho = |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|$, then $Y = 1$ with probability one and $\text{Var}(Y) = 0$.

Proof. Let $F = F_{W_n}(\rho)$ and $q = \text{Tr}(P_1\rho)$. As in the proof of Proposition 2, $F \leq q$. The probability of $A = 1$ is

$$p_A = \beta_n q + \nu_n F \geq \beta_n F + \nu_n F = (\beta_n + \nu_n)F = F.$$

Since $(Y - 1)^2 = 0$ on A and is at most L_n^2 on the complement,

$$\text{Var}(Y) \leq \mathbb{E}[(Y - 1)^2] \leq L_n^2(1 - p_A) \leq L_n^2(1 - F).$$

Finally $L_n \leq 2$, so $L_n^2(1 - F) \leq 4(1 - F)$. If $\rho = |W_n\rangle\langle W_n|$, then $F = 1$, so $\text{Var}(Y) = 0$. \square

7 Conclusion

In this work, we showed that verification of W states can be made much more efficient by allowing 2-local measurements. Our protocol randomly pairs the qubits, performs simple two-qubit tests on those disjoint pairs, and accepts only the measurement patterns that match the single shared excitation structure of the W state. This pair-matching method preserves perfect completeness while keeping the verification spectral gap bounded away from zero for all system sizes. As a result, the number of copies needed for reliable certification no longer grows with the number of qubits. We also showed that the verification algorithm can be used for fidelity estimation by reusing the pass indicator together with an additional single-excitation indicator. Developing symmetry-aware k -local verification and fidelity estimation strategies for other structured multipartite states remains an interesting direction for future work.

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